

ASEAN Integration Towards ASEAN Economy Community

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Abstract

The transpiring of ASEAN Economy Community will create integration in highlighting the collaboration among ASEAN countries in the aim to accomplish economy sustainability leading to economic growth. Economy integration is required to accomplish greater economy size. The ASEAN economies will have responded the competition among the society by trade in goods, trade in services and investments. AEC will give a great contribution in state of economy growth by facilitating trade and also inducing investment. Whether to intensify the initiative of new cooperation and the implementation are accelerate the integration of single market and production base, which will make a wider global supply chain.

The purpose of this paper is to examine how does AEC will impact to the way of facing the challenges in new era of rising Asian economy. Reflecting the rising economic interdependence and in response to the AEC, ASEAN should embarked on various initiatives for economic integration namely radical institution to make radical change, bold action response, opportunity cost in performing national ego contest and open up our sense of identity about ASEAN.

The paper identifies a number of challenges facing the integration, which are: (1) the insufficient ambition in our AEC plan; (2) mismatch between ASEAN plan and ASEAN capability; and also (3) structural problems, low legalization and effectiveness of overlapping regional institution.

The formula to decode the implication of integration is by restructuring aggressively, whether in the process, we also should rebranding ASEAN through AEC as a remark to break down the global market. AEC will make unleash ASEAN as the world economy leader.

Keywords: ASEAN, Integration, Economy Growth

Background

ASEAN is stand for Association of Southeast Asian Nations which consist of Indonesia, Malaysia, Singapore, Philippines, Myanmar, Cambodia, Laos, Brunei Darussalam, Vietnam and Thailand. Their purpose to be in the association because of their will to hand in hand to develop economy, socio-cultural and political-security. Thus, to achieve the integrated of developed economy, sustained welfare and prosperity, they declare ASEAN Economic Community plan which provide ASEAN member a single market for goods and services and also production base between each member to be achieved at 2015.

The importance of this integration is to make realization of economy stabilization with the following key characteristic namely a single market and production base, a highly competitive economic region, a region of equitable economic development, and a region fully integrated into the global economy. It must become an important role in the world nowadays to develop their welfare by integrated with another country. The integration of ASEAN community means that in this huge growth of global environment with interdependent markets and globalised industries, ASEAN should take actions to build the competitiveness to become stronger and play a big role in global supply chain.

ASEAN Economic Community starts from the summit of ASEAN Leaders in Kuala Lumpur in December 1997 that established ASEAN Vision 2020. The Declaration of ASEAN Concord II in Bali, Indonesia, on 7 October 2003, which decided to establish by 2020 the ASEAN Community, including the ASEAN Economic Community (AEC), is the next path to reach ASEAN Vision 2020 by forming regional economic integration. The ASEAN countries are having a strong commitment to overcome the regional economic integration plan which proven by signed the Cebu Declaration on the Acceleration of the Establishment of an ASEAN Community in the 12th ASEAN Summit in January 2007. They want to transform ASEAN into a region without barriers in the movement of goods and services, investment, skilled labor and capital by forming ASEAN Economy Community.

The start point of economy integration in ASEAN can be seen such as the easier way to go abroad to ASEAN countries without visa, less barriers of import and export of goods and services in ASEAN region and many more. Those circumstances always give big impact to economy activities in each country. The ASEAN economies are arranged to face the competition among the society by trading in goods, trade in services and investments. AEC will also give a great contribution in state of economy growth by facilitating trade and inducing investment, equitable economic development, and single market and production base. Whether to intensify the initiative of new cooperation and the implementation are accelerated the integration of single market and production base, which will make a wider global supply chain. We likely will be more productive and gain more profit. The flow of goods and services also will be much higher than before. The growth of economy will attract more investors to invest their money in Indonesia that will impact to higher production and improvements. The flows of skilled labor are going to be more scattered and the flow of capital will growth rapidly. Those impacts will give simultaneous incentives to ASEAN countries' economy. This papers provide the analysis on how the ASEAN Economic Community will create such a longterm sustainability among the members toward the future economic development.

Analysis and Founding Datas

Asean Economy Community (AEC) is the new way purposed by ASEAN countries regarding for the recent fenomenon happened and the most spoken issues such as free trade. Economy integration is required to accomplish greater economy size. The ASEAN economies will have responded the competition among the society by trading in goods, trade in services and investments. AEC will give a great contribution in state of economy growth by facilitating trade and inducing investment, equitable economic development, and single market and production base. Whether to intensify the initiative of new cooperation and the

implementation are accelerated the integration of single market and production base, which will make a wider global supply chain.

Diagram 1. Asean Economy Community Blueprint

Source: Asean Economy Community Blueprint, 2008 (organised)

Competitive Economic Region

Looking at the role of AEC as a trigger in increasing the trade among ASEAN countries will simply give a positive impression considering some barriers in trade will be eliminated. One thing that have been debated almost everytime when the word free trade come up is the unbalanced competition happening between the developed and developing countries. However, each countries are seeking for the different economic interests, the international cooperation is established for facilitating the distribution of common benefits among patners in the fairest manner. For example the ACFTA conquered an agreement between Indonesia and China gave both side of these countries great benefit for this integration. Indonesia has recovered such a greater market for its product with billions of China's citizens. It allows Indonesia to reach a great number of consumers in order to become a prior for the local industry to be creative and innovative in creating new product. While China grabs a lot profit because it has unique and cheap products hunted by consumers.

The ASEAN Economic Community is giving incentives to the economy system in each country to make their best efforts for higher achievements. The incentives obtained by free flow of goods and services, free flow of investments, free flow of skilled labor and free flow of capital. People will tend to be more productive and innovative. Tariff reduction and trade facilitation are one of the stimulus for people to work more and produce more. ASEAN has made tariff barriers become significantly reduced and user-friendly Rules of Origin to facilitate trade and intensify business development in ASEAN region. Governments also made rules to enhance key trade agreements such as the ASEAN Trade in Goods Agreement

(ATIGA), which substitute the 1993 Agreement on the Common Effective Preferential Tariff Scheme for the ASEAN free trade area and ASEAN still working towards establishing an ASEAN Single Area.

In the other hand, ASEAN Economic Community will makes government in each country hand-in-hand to work together, rather than compete with each other. This occurrence in some points can discourage people to work more and produce more because of the decrease in competitiveness degree in trade and other aspects as well. The differences of economy condition in each country also can be obstacles in the course of the formation of the ASEAN Economic Community. Some aspects of the ASEAN region looks not ready, such as export intra-ASEAN is still low, FDI intra-ASEAN is still low or even the contribution of ASEAN countries in trade are not evenly yet.

Tabel 1. Intra and Extra ASEAN Trade (value in US\$ million; share in percent)

Country	Intra-ASEAN exports		Extra-ASEAN exports		Total exports	Intra-ASEAN imports		Extra-ASEAN imports		Total imports
	Value	Share to total exports	Value	Share to total exports		Value	Share to total imports	Value	Share to total imports	
Brunei Darussalam	1,229.3	17.1	5,939.3	82.9	7,168.6	1,242.8	51.8	1,156.8	48.2	2,399.6
Cambodia	644.6	12.9	4,341.2	87.1	4,985.8	1,453.3	37.3	2,447.6	62.7	3,900.9
Indonesia	24,623.9	21.1	91,886.1	78.9	116,510.0	27,742.4	28.7	69,086.8	71.3	96,829.2
Lao PDR	997.4	80.6	239.8	19.4	1,237.2	1,480.8	85.8	244.2	14.2	1,725.0
Malaysia	40,365.1	25.7	116,525.8	74.3	156,890.9	31,700.2	25.7	91,630.2	74.3	123,330.5
Myanmar	3,196.7	50.4	3,144.8	49.6	6,341.5	2,065.7	53.7	1,784.1	46.3	3,849.9
Philippines	5,838.4	15.2	32,496.2	84.8	38,334.7	11,561.1	25.4	33,972.9	74.6	45,533.9
Singapore	81,646.5	30.3	188,186.0	69.7	269,832.5	59,047.6	24.0	186,737.1	76.0	245,784.7
Thailand	32,490.6	21.3	120,006.6	78.7	152,497.2	26,759.5	20.0	107,010.1	80.0	133,769.6
Viet Nam	8,554.8	15.1	48,136.2	84.9	56,691.0	13,566.7	19.6	55,664.2	80.4	69,230.9
ASEAN	199,587.3	24.6	610,901.9	75.4	810,489.2	176,620.1	24.3	549,734.0	75.7	726,354.1

Source: ASEAN Merchandise Trade Statistics Database (compiled/computed from data submission, publications and/or websites of ASEAN Member States' national ASEAN Free Trade Area (AFTA) units, national statistics offices, customs departments/agencies, or central banks), 2009

Tabel 2. ASEAN Trade 2008-2009 (value in US\$ million; change in percent)

Country	2008			2009 ^{1/}			Year-on-year change		
	Exports	Imports	Total trade	Exports	Imports	Total trade	Exports	Imports	Total trade
Brunei Darussalam	10,268.0	2,506.7	12,774.7	7,168.6	2,399.6	9,568.2	(30.2)	(4.3)	(25.1)
Cambodia	4,358.5	4,417.0	8,775.6	4,985.8	3,900.9	8,886.7	14.4	(11.7)	1.3
Indonesia	137,020.4	129,197.3	266,217.7	116,510.0	96,829.2	213,339.2	(15.0)	(25.1)	(19.9)
Lao PDR	827.7	1,803.2	2,630.9	1,237.2	1,725.0	2,962.1	49.5	(4.3)	12.6
Malaysia	194,495.9	144,298.8	338,794.7	156,890.9	123,330.5	280,221.4	(19.3)	(14.5)	(17.3)
Myanmar	6,620.6	3,794.9	10,415.4	6,341.5	3,849.9	10,191.3	(4.2)	1.4	(2.2)

The Philippines	49,025.4	56,645.6	105,671.0	38,334.7	45,533.9	83,868.6	(21.8)	(19.6)	(20.6)
Singapore	338,175.9	319,780.3	657,956.2	269,832.5	245,784.7	515,617.1	(20.2)	(23.1)	(21.6)
Thailand	174,966.7	177,567.5	352,534.2	152,497.2	133,769.6	286,266.8	(12.8)	(24.7)	(18.8)
Viet Nam	61,777.8	79,579.2	141,357.0	56,691.0	69,230.9	125,921.9	(8.2)	(13.0)	(10.9)
ASEAN	977,536.9	919,590.5	1,897,127.5	810,489.2	726,354.1	1,536,843.3	(17.1)	(21.0)	(19.0)

Source: ASEAN Merchandise Trade Statistics Database (compiled/computed from data submission, publications and/or websites of ASEAN Member States' national ASEAN Free Trade Area (AFTA) units, national statistics offices, customs departments/agencies, or central banks), 2009

The challenge that ASEAN nation have to pursue now are increasing the intra-ASEAN trade to gain more incentives and take the advantages of opportunities of developing ASEAN. From the data above, we can see that intra-ASEAN trade is still low or even the contribution of ASEAN countries in trade are not evenly yet. The dispersion of trade numbers intra-ASEAN shows that we must work hard to developing ASEAN into a wider global supply chain.

ASEAN Economic Community will bring a new direction of the competition atmosphere in ASEAN region by giving insight for business to expand their production, become bigger and more profitable. The wider market for goods and services, investments, skilled labor and capital will provide every people to take the opportunities and encourage them to be innovative. People also have to work efficiently because the competitiveness situation is become more intense. This situation will lead into a condition where the economy situation force people to be full of innovation and have to do that in an efficient way. The competitiveness of economy condition will also give advantages to customers in each country. They will have a lot of choices for goods and services that being produced. Businesses also get the advantages by having free flow of investments, capital and skilled labor. It makes they have plenty of choices to produce more efficiently.

ASEAN will also get challenges to bring off ASEAN Economic Community plan. When business getting into tighter competitive atmosphere, the people will be more effectively to make decisions, include the recruitment of labor. The competition to getting a job will be much harder than before. Labor force of a country will combined with labor force from other countries to find a job. If governments in ASEAN countries do not provide enough job opportunities for labor force, the rivalry of find a job will be much higher and difficult. The unemployment rate will be increase because of this circumstance. Unemployment will become increasingly widespread and it will give bad impacts to the society. In the long run, the criminal problem will rise because of the increase of unemployment. When a lot of people become unemployment, they tend to be more criminal to provide their needs of money. It also will give impacts in social-cultural area in the society. The uniqueness of every region will start to blend and there is a possibility of conflict will arise. The integration will also generate people to be work harder, beyond their ability, to make the opportunities into reality. ASEAN Economic Community pushes people to give the best efforts and in the mean time, we believe that they will become more understand to each other, to each nation in ASEAN for the integration.

Trade barriers for ASEAN countries are being reduced to accomplish a free flow of goods and services. From 1 January 2010, all tariffs for products in the Common Effective Preferential Tariff (CEPT) count Brunei Darussalam, Indonesia, Malaysia, Philippines, Singapore and Thailand, which representing 99 percent of total tariff lines, have been eliminated for intra-ASEAN trade. The rules of origin are also being simplified to facilitate trade and enhance business development in the region. But actually, the governments still have to concern about non-tariff barriers, which can disrupt the improvements and planning for ASEAN Economic Community. Free flow of services are also provide for business services, professional services, construction, distribution, education, environmental services, healthcare, maritime transport, telecommunication and tourism. The investments flow will be more attractive with greater benefits through a more comprehensive investment agreement include the investment guarantees. ASEAN also develop an integrated ASEAN capital market to achieve freer flow of capital. The single market resolution has to be implemented to achieve the purpose of ASEAN Economic Community.

Single Market and Production Base

An attempt to increase the number of investment is also one of the things needed to spotlight in emerging these ASEAN countries. Living in multipolar when integration becomes a must requires some countries to be productive and open for some foreign direct investment. Investment plays such a big role in constructing strong foundation for a country economic development. The more money invested in a country, the bigger entrepreneur opportunities served by a nation. This investment will open a lot chances for the business to open some job opportunity and indulge the people to start a business by serving some capital. The role of AEC in opening more spaces to develop for nations will touch some unreachable layers which at the end of the day leads to the economic growth. Reflecting lesson from ACFTA that implemented in Indonesia. We are able to analyze the providing data in order to see the increasing in investment for the single market between Indonesia and China.

Tabel 3. Indonesian Average Trade Before and After ACFTA

Country	Before ACFTA				After ACFTA				
	2002	2003	2004	Average	2005	2006	2007	2008	Average
ASEAN	299,2	464,1	916,2	559,83	2250	926,7	4028,4	1855,7	2265
China	6	83,2	8,1	32,43	37,3	31,5	28,9	139,6	59,33
Total	305,2	547,3	924,3	592,26	2287,3	958,2	4057,3	1995,3	2324,33
% China Invesment to Indonesia	0,002	0,005	0,002	0,006	0,004	0,005	0,003	0,009	0,006

Source: Indonesia Investment Coordinating Board, 2009 (not including investment in oil and natural gas)

Tabel 4. Development of Investment Realization China to Indonesia 2001-2007 (million U.S.\$)

Indicator	Before ACFTA (2002-2004)	After ACFTA (2005-2008)
Export	3110,07	7940,79
oil and natural gas	954,7	2794,38
non-oil and non-natural gas	2815,37	5146,41
Import	3162,06	6780,98
oil and natural gas	563,98	1001,87
non-oil and non-natural gas	2598,08	5779,11
Trade Balance	608,01	1159,81
oil and natural gas	390,72	1792,51
non-oil and non-natural gas	217,29	-632,7
Total	6932,13	14721,78
oil and natural gas	1518,68	3796,25
non-oil and non-natural gas	5413,45	10925,53

Source: Statistics Indonesia, 2009

We are able to see that there are such increasing happened between these countries related to the implemented regulation for these countries. In implementing ACFTA, it provides both of countries single market including Indonesia and China citizens. Single market will encourage the industries to produce more products to fulfill the consumer demand. More demand, more profit will be gained. It will also happen in the realization of Asean Economy Community. Every country will go beyond the unity of single market and increase their investment.

Equitable Economic Development

Diversion of the trade numbers between ASEAN members is a challenge for every nation to give their best efforts to developing each other production and trade so we can achieve the goals of ASEAN Economic Community. The ways to develop the economy are enhance SME development and build the Initiative for ASEAN Integration (IAI). SME development are needed because of the promising development of SME can build more profitable production and make a wider global supply chain. The ASEAN Policy Blueprint for SME Development (APBSD) 2004-2014 are the first action to achieve the equitable economic development. The positive indications of expanding ASEAN countries shown by the various efforts to developing SME in ASEAN region in some areas, such as easier access to information, market, human resource development and skills, finance and technology. The compactness of ASEAN countries are needed to strengthen the ASEAN SMEs to facing global business environment which will give a contribution to ASEAN economic growth and development.

Other way to develop equitable economy is enhance the Initiative for ASEAN Integration. The purpose of Initiative for ASEAN Integration are to spread evenly the development of ASEAN countries so that the benefits of ASEAN integration are shared by all ASEAN member countries. The Initiative for ASEAN Integration was made to gives direction to reduce the development gap of ASEAN member countries which covers infrastructure, human resource development, information and communications technologies (ICT), capacity building for regional economic integration, energy, investment climate, tourism, poverty reduction and improvement in the quality of life. This plan require more developed countries in ASEAN, Indonesia, Thailand, Malaysia, Philipines, Brunei Darussalam and Singapore to continously support CMLV (Cambodia, Myanmar, Laos and Vietnam) to enhance economic growth, strengthen economic competitiveness, increase deomestic and foreign direct investments and expand private sector enterprises to achieve the integration of ASEAN.

Integratio into the Global Economy

In related with the ASEAN economic development, one thing needed to be examined is how AEC will face the challenges in new era of rising ASEAN economy. Reflecting the rising economic interdependence and in response to the AEC, ASEAN should embarked on various initiatives for economic integration namely radical institution to make radical change, bold action response, opportunity cost in performing national ego contest and open up our sense of identity about ASEAN. National ego usually appear as new barries hampering this integration. The local government always want to apply protectionism for its country in the name to protect local industry not to lose the ferocious competitons ended to collapse. Even this fact usually realize in some countries, but there must be such a positive energy that leads these nations to be open minded as a trigger for the government to encourage its local industry to be more competitive to face the global market. This is why the existence of radical institution is demanded to control the main barrier in collaborating these countries. National ego should be eradicated in order to achieve the integration as the action of bold response toward AEC.

There are also some challenges facing the integration includes the insufficient ambition in our AEC plan, mismatch between ASEAN plan and ASEAN capability and also structural problems, low legalization and effectiveness of overlapping regional institution. Ambition is very important in indulging each nation to be cooperative to implement the AEC. Ambition will motivate every nation to participate in melting and fixing its local regulation regarding the new global regulation related to the realization of AEC. If the ambition is strong, the structural problems will contribute minimal effect for the realization because it will lead to the high legalization involving the government and society of a country. High legalization will embrace the AEC identity in minimizing the overlapping in local institution in order to tackle all of the challenges.

Conclusion

AEC as the way to go to the economy growth for the ASEAN countries will make the economy will be sustainable if 4 factors are bounded as a unity. AEC will lead ASEAN toward single market and production base, **integration into the global economy, equitable economic development, and competitive economic region.** The ASEAN economies will

have responded the competition among the society by trade in goods, trade in services and investments. AEC will give a great contribution in state of economy growth by facilitating trade and also inducing investment. Whether to intensify the initiative of new cooperation and the implementation are accelerate the integration of single market and production base, which will make a wider global supply chain. **There are some challenges will be hampered this way include the legalization, national ego, and low implementation. But in spirit toward global economy growth, Asean Economy Community will lead the ASEAN countries for the economy sustainability.** The formula to decode the implication of integration is by restructuring aggressively, whether in the process, we also should rebranding ASEAN through AEC as a remark to break down the global market. AEC will make unleash ASEAN as the world economy leader.

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